

CALL TO ACTION

Ethical partnerships for
collaborative action and learning

JULY 2023

THE CHALLENGE

“We had to ask ourselves who would benefit from this collaboration and to what extent”

“We are into it together to create a better world for people”.

“We've had this unique opportunity to really to find out more about the kinds of structures and processes and supports that are needed ...to enable the democratisation of knowledge”

Historically, there has been a tendency for South-North research partnerships to be marked by inequitable power relations.

The traditional, colonial model of research is one in which Northern partners have often been in an advantageous position to frame research questions in relation to Northern agendas, epistemologies and development frames and to dominate research collaborations through superior access to research funding, publishing and other opportunities. Southern partners have often adopted secondary roles, as collectors of data rather than as equal partners in the research process. Traditional North-South partnership approaches can also limit the possibilities for South-South and South-North learning.

THE CHALLENGE

Traditional approaches to capacity development have taken a deficit view of Southern capacities.

'Capacities' are often understood narrowly as the ability to understand and apply existing, established research methods. This limits opportunities for methodological development based on the lived experiences, contexts and epistemologies of the global South, reproducing power imbalances and impoverishing the research process as a whole. Moving beyond Northern approaches creates the potential for adopting new approaches and developing mutual capacities, based on the lived experiences, contexts and epistemologies of the global South.

Traditional processes of evaluation often assess success against pre-determined criteria linked to Northern development frames and priorities.

Conducting research that is co-created with communities requires research teams to continuously monitor and adapt to complex and changing realities. By prioritising pre-defined project outcomes, traditional approaches to evaluation (including the use of log frames) limit opportunities for ongoing reflection and learning about the research process and thus opportunities to adapt to new, often unforeseen challenges.

WHAT NEEDS TO BE TAKEN SERIOUSLY

... evidence informed
recommendations for
ethical partnerships

TESF has sought to foreground the perspectives and priorities of communities and practitioners in the South, in contrast to traditional approaches to research partnerships, capacity building and evaluation - a knowledge production ecosystem which continues to favour Northern partners. The path to equitable and transformative partnership working is illustrated below:

1. Co-create the research agenda.

The proposal for our network was co-created between the country partners in 2019. Through discussion, research questions were identified, the co-creation methodological approach was adopted and project leadership strategies were suggested. Constraints were still felt on the equitable intent of this collaborative process as the funder's required a UK-based institution to formally 'lead' on the application and conform to UK funding criteria for ethics and due diligence with no expectation that partners could conduct their own due diligence on Bristol or the funding body.

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2. Create a flat rather than hierarchical network structure.

The network was established to support locally-led, action-oriented research for education in India, Rwanda, Somalia/Somaliland and South Africa. To prioritise local agency while maintaining the necessary level of coherence across the network, a 'hub and spokes' structure was adopted. Country hubs were involved in all stages of decision-making through their representation on the leadership team allowing for mutual support and accountability. This democratic approach to leadership stood in contrast to top down models of partnership working and fostered ownership of the research at a country level built on a deep knowledge of context and culturally embedded relationships.

Hubs in the global South were responsible for establishing and sustaining a programme of research relevant to their own country contexts. At a network level, this required flexibility in implementing network activities in different ways. It also relied on open communication and processes of mutual learning, underpinned by values of trust and reciprocity.

TESF network model reflecting principles of distributed and endogenous systems leadership

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3. Foreground local agendas and agency.

After launching the TESF network in January 2020, a series of 'engagement events' were held online and in-person in each of the hub countries with national and regional-level policy actors; practitioners based in educational institutions; representatives from NGOs and civil society organisations; and university-based researchers to share priorities for that could feed into the *Call for Proposals*. Across all hub countries, support was offered for those with limited prior experience of research and grant applications. Rather than adopting a one-size-fits all approach to the *Call for Proposals*, ethical partnership working required flexibility to meet contextual demands. At the hub level, working with historically disadvantaged groups required differentiated support, which in some cases involved the collaborative development of proposals between project teams and hub staff and language support. While three of the four hubs opted for an 'open' call, due to political sensitivities Somalia/Somaliland decided to take an invitational approach with a focus on those representing historically marginalised groups.

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4. Take a distributed, asset-based view of capacities.

The network brought together a wide range of actors including NGOs, civil society organisations, universities, schools, colleges, government organisations at different levels, and from business and the arts. Ethical working required recognising the complementarity of knowledge and skills, and mobilising these in service of shared agendas. **Hubs** took an active role in mobilising and strengthening capacities, through organising retreats for experience-sharing and collaborative analysis between projects. In the complex political environment of Somalia/Somaliland, structures were put in place to provide regional-level support for teams. At the **network level**, access to optional opportunities was provided for knowledge exchange and collaboration within the network. A community of practice (CoP) model fostered relationships between funded projects and the wider network, for mutual support (intellectual, emotional, practical, etc.), and a cross-national forum for sharing knowledge and experiences. Project outputs in a range of forms was also encouraged and supported, using media and languages appropriate to their audiences.

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5. Support ongoing monitoring, evaluation and learning (MEL) based on projects' own ambitions.

To foreground local agendas, we collaboratively developed a 'values-centred' MEL approach, based on the view that the evaluation was best judged by those directly involved in the activities. A framework was developed, indicating five domains which TEF sought to impact: *People and Relationships, Capacities, Knowledge, Outputs and Sharing, Outcomes and Legacies* and project teams were invited to develop their own "ambition statements". The values-centred approach allowed project teams to pursue their own agendas, in contrast to the more common compliance-based MEL log-frames. Across the network, projects had extremely varied ambitions from their work. Whilst such an approach is immensely valuable, careful thought and planning and dedicated resources needs to go into its implementation.

CALL TO ACTION

What we ALL need to do TOGETHER ...

EVERYONE has a role to play in transforming education for sustainable futures for ALL living on our planet ...

What role are **you** playing?

Transforming Education for Sustainable Futures in a way that serves the interest of historically marginalised groups has important implications for partnership working, capacity mobilisation and monitoring evaluation and learning.

- **For Researchers:** Embrace equitable partnership working, capacity mobilisation and monitoring evaluation and learning processes, through foregrounding local agendas and agency and opening spaces for collaboration which are minimally distorted by power relations. Support research teams with the knowledge, understanding, time and resources that will enable them to benefit from these approaches.
- **For funding councils:** Reform the way that funding calls are designed and implemented to redress Northern biases in the processes and outcomes of research.
- **For Universities:** Establish policies that are [consistent with principles of transformative partnership working](#) between researchers in the global North and South.

THANK YOU!!

Visit our website:
www.tesf.network

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Transforming Education
for Sustainable Futures

This CALL TO ACTION, compiled by Rafael Mitchell, Leon Tikly and Rhona Brown is based on the findings of 67 co-engaged research projects implemented across four countries in the Transforming Education for Futures Project involving four Network hubs in South Africa, India, Somalia / Somaliland, Rwanda. Overall co-ordination was provided by, and supported by the University of Bristol and partners, with UKRI with GCRF funding. The Network was also supported and complemented by substantive in-kind support and collegial relations that contributed significantly to the Network's outcomes and success through intellectual, social, economic, ethical and other contributions.

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